

Visualizing supercomputer node status on Open OnDemand with Plotly

Jason Yalim
yalim@asu.edu
Arizona State University
Tempe, Arizona, USA

ABSTRACT

The Sol supercomputer provides Arizona State University researchers access to a state-of-the-art system with an observed GPU-only High Performance Linpack speed of 2.42 PetaFLOP/s. This short paper details the implementation of a popular Plotly-powered status page that is accessible by Sol’s users through the Open OnDemand interface. The page is automatically updated once a minute and abstracts supercomputer nodes as squares that are colored by their SLURM status. GPU status is further indicated with subset circle symbols, that are either empty (idle) or filled (allocated). GPU slicing through NVIDIA’s multi instance GPU (MIG) software is also indicated by circles that fill proportionally to the allocation. The source code is provided online with an open-source license [1].

KEYWORDS

High performance computing, high throughput computing, supercomputers, clusters, science gateways, scientific applications, user support, Open OnDemand applications, node status pages, HPC dashboards

Reference Format:

Jason Yalim. 2024. Visualizing supercomputer node status on Open OnDemand with Plotly. In *Rocky Mountain Advanced Computing Consortium HPC Symposium (RMACC24)*, May 21–23, 2024, Boulder, CO, USA. RMACC, Boulder, CO, USA, 5 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10975832>

1 INTRODUCTION

Arizona State University (ASU) operates campus high-performance computing (HPC) systems funded through periodic university investments. The most recent addition was the Sol supercomputer, which was presented during the RMACC23 HPC Symposium and heavily detailed in a PEARC23 short paper [2, 3]. During both presentations, the custom node-status page for Sol drew positive attention from other institutions that had an interest in providing their own staff and researchers with an Open OnDemand (OOD) accessible status page powered by Plotly [4, 5], and led to a presentation for OOD’s October 5, 2023 Tips and Tricks call.

The status page provides a high-level abstraction of the supercomputer’s current state via a heat map based on SLURM node status. It is regularly monitored by system administrators to assess system health. The visualization also illustrates GPU allocations and provides a hover text with node details that improve the quality

of life of researchers that wish to understand and use heterogeneous node types. The status page supplements other commonly utilized and powerful visualization tools like Prometheus, Telegraf, InfluxDB, Ganglia, or Grafana [6–12] in that it is accessible as a simple sub-page on the supercomputer’s OOD-powered web portal, keeping end-users within a single environment and helping them digest what the supercomputer really is. While many centers have their own internal status pages, the majority are not documented in the literature and remain isolated, making a comprehensive review of existing implementations difficult. To the best of the author’s knowledge, the presented visualization is unique among HPC centers due to the OOD-implementation. This short paper provides low-level details on ASU’s status page and its implementation, as well as the motivation for its creation, in the hopes that other centers are better able to reproduce or build off of these efforts.

2 BACKGROUND

ASU’s latest supercomputer, Sol, was preceded by a number of smaller clusters. These clusters were graphically monitored by a set of custom raw-HTML, PHP, and MySQL powered web services that ran on a staff-maintained virtual machine (RCSTATUS). The PHP code would query several databases, including the main `slurm_acct_db` but also a custom `slurm_aux_db` that provided additional details about the system and its users. Figure 1 is a screenshot of the RCSTATUS landing page for the previous flagship supercomputer, Agave, illustrating how the portal was responsible for multiple abstractions of system services. RCSTATUS, which was behind the University’s single sign-on authentication service, could provide administrators internal information about the system and was widely utilized by researchers to see the status of their own condo nodes or the wider system.

Figure 2 is a screenshot of the node status page for the previous flagship supercomputer, Agave. The PHP-status page would query the database on every page load and automatically refresh once every minute, looping over arrays of SLURM partitions to build the status partitions, and would conduct simple sums across all nodes and jobs to provide summaries of partition utilization as well as the number of pending or allocated jobs. The node status page load was initially snappy, but near the end of its life, page loading times increased to 30+ seconds. This was likely due to degradation in the custom database after the original author and maintainer left ASU in 2021.

The previous node status page established a set of features that any new status page would need to keep, as well as a set of lessons to reiterate on. The set of features to keep included (1) the simple summaries of system status, (2) the abstraction of nodes and GPUs with color and symbols to indicate allocation status, (3) and the

This paper is published under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0) license. Authors reserve their rights to disseminate the work on their personal and corporate Web sites with the appropriate attribution.

RMACC24, May 21–23, 2024, Boulder, CO, USA

© 2024 IW3C2 (International World Wide Web Conference Committee), published under Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0 License.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10975832>

ASU is contributing cluster/node idle time to the community-driven Folding@Home COVID-19 research efforts under the rcfahuser account. These jobs are submitted in the lowest priority QOS queue and will be automatically cancelled to make resources available to any user-submitted jobs. The rcfahuser jobs should never impact user jobs or research.

By running these computations only during truly idle time, Research Computing is able to contribute to COVID modeling efforts without impacting ASU's everyday computational research.

Agave Documentation

- [Official Docs \(Confluence\)](#)
- [New User Guide](#)
- [Getting an account on Agave](#)

Agave Status Information

- [Concise Agave Cluster Status Page](#)
- [Long Agave Cluster Status Page](#)
- [Offline Nodes](#)
- [Offline Nodes \(NHC\)](#)
- [Offline Nodes \(Kill task failed\)](#)

My Agave Jobs

- [My Currently Running Jobs](#)
- [My Currently Pending Jobs](#)
- [My Jobs Completed in Last 24 Hours](#)

All Agave Jobs

- [All Currently Running Jobs](#)
- [All Currently Pending Jobs](#)
- [All Jobs Completed in Last 24 Hours](#)
- [Successfully Completed Jobs in Last 24 Hours](#)
- [Jobs Preempted in Last 24 Hours](#)
- [Jobs Cancelled in Last 24 Hours](#)
- [Jobs with "Failed" Completion Code in Last 24 Hours](#)
- [Jobs with "Node Fail" Completion Code in Last 24 Hours](#)
- [Jobs with "Timeout" Completion Code in Last 24 Hours](#)
- [Search for a particular JobID](#)

Need Help?

Figure 1. A screenshot of the legacy, in-house graphical status monitoring website for the progenitor supercomputer, Agave. The page provided all system users access to many different PHP generated views of the supercomputer and its status, and served as a source for documentation prior to a switch to Atlassian’s Confluence. System administrators would make use of the offline node pages in addition to the concise status page which was also popular with users.

Figure 2. An example of the legacy, in-house node status page that motivated the deployment of a similar service for the new flagship supercomputer, Sol. Major system partitions were partitioned on the page (the primary parallel partition is shown in the figure). Nodes were abstracted as CSS-drawn rectangles that were colored by SLURM status and annotated by the node’s short hostname. Using the mouse to hover over a node resulted in a hovertext that provided details on that node, its hardware utilization, and how to access it via SLURM constraints and partitions. GPU nodes are not shown, but utilized empty (idle) or filled (allocated) circle symbols to in the bottom-left corner of the node rectangle to indicate GPU availability.

detailed hovertext. With the implementation of Open OnDemand (OOD), an additional web service like RCSTATUS seemed overbearing on the average user. One requirement was for any new node status page to be directly viewable on the OOD web portal. Additionally, the load on the SLURM databases from multiple users doing periodic page loads of the RCSTATUS page was undesirable, which would be avoided by utilizing a cached, single snapshot of the system status to be served at user request. Finally, there was a

desire to avoid as much in-house code as possible, and to rely on sophisticated, externally maintained packages when available.

3 THE NEW NODE STATUS PAGE

The new node status page is driven by shell and python scripts that live adjacent to software packages on a system-wide, globally mounted filesystem (i.e., /packages/public/sol-node-status). The node status page’s data are pulled from SLURM (version 24 [13]) and plotted by Python via an every-minute crontab run (on an

Figure 3. An example of Sol’s node status page, as part of the Open OnDemand (OOD) web portal. Each square is a compute node; color indicates SLURM status. Filled or empty circles indicate allocated or idle GPUs, respectively. The two multi instance GPU (MIG) nodes are *g048* and *g049*, in the last two rows of the second to last column, indicating that three ten-GiB MIG nodes are allocated on the first and second GPUs of *g048* (the MIG slices are served in sevenths of the main A100s). A hovertext provides node details for *c037*, which is fully allocated due to all 128 physical cores being requested (despite 103 GiB of RAM remaining unscheduled, entirely idle and inefficient), is schedule-able in the ‘general’ or ‘htc’ partitions, with a full and healthy CPU load of 128.21 but only 37 GiB of the possible 400 allocated GiB actually in use. An interactive demonstration is available online [1, view demo button in readme].

Figure 4. Screenshot of Sol’s Open OnDemand (OOD) page. The System dropdown is activated, and “Sol Status” — which links to figure 3 — is highlighted by a hovering mouse. Getting the node status page working with OOD resulted in the other two visible system apps, “Available Modules” and “Storage Quotas.” The former links to a DataTables.js-powered static HTML page of Sol’s software modules, allowing researchers to quickly (from the browser) query if the software they need is available. The latter links to a simple wrapper of a shell command that shows researchers how much of their limited storage they are using.

administrative virtual machine as an unprivileged user, `software`), that is,

```
* * * * * /packages/public/sol-node-status/get-sol-node-status.sh \
&> /packages/public/sol-node-status/crontab.diag
```

The above script automates the entire data curation and plot loop. To generate scheduler and job statistics, a helper script [1, `./bin/local-sq-stats`] calls the SLURM tool `squeue` with a special format string that’s passed to GNU `awk` for processing. The results (the number of unique users in the queue, the number of running jobs, the number of pending jobs, and the total number of jobs) are saved to disk via redirect.

To actually determine node status and information, the SLURM tool `sinfo` is called twice in order to quickly grab orthogonal system information. The first call passes “short format” tokens to `sinfo` and the second passed “long format” tokens. The “long format” tokens are an exhaustive list of all possible outputs to get from `sinfo`, however, the “short format” tokens will sometimes have a nicer output. For instance, the “REASON” field is better retrieved as `'%E'` as the “long format” tokens cannot be decorated with symbols like quotations, otherwise making it difficult to parse a “REASON” with blank spaces in it. The “long format” also provides generic resource utilization information, which was useful to retrieve with generous padding (some fields were truncated to 21-characters by default, an undocumented surprise). The results from the two `sinfo` calls are pasted together and redirected into a node status snapshot file with the assumption that the node order will remain the same between the two simultaneous calls. A future release could write the results to separate temporary files that are easily merged by `awk` or Python’s `pandas` module, or directly query the SLURM database.

The node status visualization Python script [1, `./plot-sol-node-status.py`] now has all the data it needs. Please note that the majority of the script defines layout customization for the final status page, utilizing exploded dictionaries for the serialization key-value pairs on unique lines as to increase readability and improve the ability to make changes or leave comments. For instance, using

version `0.10.1` for reference, lines 211–271 explicitly assign background and text colors to every node state, while lines 186–203 use a doc-string to define custom hovertext (using Plotly’s positional `{customdata[#]}` style for including dynamic information, which are named in an exploded list `COLS` on lines 25–38). Also lines 46–184 are used to parse GPU information, where the method `mig_disk` draws representations of NVIDIA multi instance GPU (MIG) resources on the status page (see `g048`, `g049` in figure 3). Note as well that `get_gpu_info` is capable of automatically parsing nodes with heterogeneous GPU types.

Otherwise, the node status snapshot data are normalized using `pandas.DataFrame` operations and certain text is reformatted (GRES data in particular) or values calculated (active RAM on a node is calculated from the difference of the retrieved free memory from the total memory). Once the text is made to be more human readable, the nodes are plotted on a scatter plot as large square markers that are individually colored by Plotly based on the SLURM state of the node. The position of the nodes in the scatter plot are calculated explicitly on lines 327 and 328. In deployment, the scatter plot offers nice interactive and accessibility-friendly features, such as isolating different nodes based on their SLURM state by clicking on legend entries. However, the choice becomes cumbersome for annotations in excess of the node’s short hostname, i.e., the GPU statuses as indicated by circles are simply drawn over their respective hosts rather than being scatter-marker object attributes. This leads to ‘ghost’ symbols if a node is removed from the view by selecting its state in the status legend as the scatter marker disappears but the GPU annotation remains. Modifying Plotly’s scatter implementation was beyond the scope of this work, but an additional attribute to append annotations would be greatly appreciated.

The python script’s Plotly call ultimately generates a static HTML page with an embedded javascript figure that is saved as a temporary file. To make this work better in deployment, the temporary file is read by `awk` and decorated with a `<head>` to automatically refresh the HTML page every 30 seconds (so users do not have to refresh the page manually to see the latest node status) which is then piped to `sed` to set a background `<body>` color, which is finally saved as the final HTML page.

The bash script then checks to see if it should keep the snapshot data just generated. The script is currently configured to only save every tenth snapshot. When saving, the raw snapshot data are compressed using `zstd` with the highest level compression of 19. The result is significant as can be seen in table 1: for the months of May, June, and July of 2023, roughly 4000 pairs of snapshots were saved, resulting in over 1.2 GB of raw data that was instead stored as 20 MB of over 8000 `zstd`-compressed files. At the end of each month, these compressed files are then uncompressed into an archive directory named `archive/%Y-%m`, and transiently tarred into a single `zstd`-compressed file, resulting in final disk weights of ~15 MB. A helper script for automating this will be provided in the supplement. These data are archived as to provide a history of the system’s status over time. An example animation from such archive data is included in the supplement’s README [3].

To include the resulting Plotly generated HTML file on Open OnDemand required relatively simple changes. First, since the HTML file is available on a system-wide filesystem mount, it was simple

Month	# snapshot pairs	raw size	before archive size	archive size
May	4352	1.2 GB	20 MB	14 MB
June	4316	1.2 GB	20 MB	15 MB
July	4464	1.3 GB	21 MB	14 MB

Table 1. For three months in 2023, storage weight of snapshots saved every ten-minutes on disk at different life cycle stages. The data are never stored in their raw format, but the raw size is included for completeness. Disk usage was measured with `du --si --apparent-size`.

to symbolically link it to `/var/www/ood/public` with the system provisioner, salt [14]. Second, the system status app’s `layout.erb` was the only file necessary to modify [1, `./provisioning/layout.erb`], which required only adding an iframe pointing at the symbolic link `/public/sol.html`. Figure 3 is taken from OOD after selecting the “Sol Status” “System Information” option as illustrated in the OOD home page screenshot in figure 4.

4 CONCLUSION

Details for an in-production supercomputer node status visualization that’s accessible from Open OnDemand (OOD) were provided. The general steps for reproduction on other systems would include, (1) cloning the supplemental repository [1] to a system-wide filesystem mount as an unprivileged user, (2) modifying the Python script to adjust for the target system, (3) running the shell script to tune the visualization, (4) linking the HTML file to the OOD services local filesystems, (5) creating or modifying a system status OOD app to include the HTML file as an iframe (with a descriptive legend below the main grid), (6) and then from an administrative node or virtual machine (still as an unprivileged user) creating a cron entry in the crontab to automatically update the status HTML page. It is highly recommended that steps (5,6) are codified through a system provisioner.

Since implementing the status page as a stopgap in 2021, both system administrators and researchers have grown accustomed to it, and external institutions have implemented it. There are many software improvements that may be done to the underlying implementation, especially for use outside of Arizona State University, such as hyper parameterization of the scripting so that host institutions may just configure a meta YAML file to obtain what they need.

While this page does one job fairly well – visually representing the status of a supercomputer – there are many features that are missing from the Plotly-powered static HTML. A natural evolution of this page would be a dynamic dashboard built with a modern javascript framework, like React. Additionally, the use of the Slurm API would allow for dynamic content generation without requiring custom databases nor Python normalization. Work is underway on a third-generation supercomputer dashboard page that incorporates the features and lessons learned from the first-generation RCSTATUS and this second-generation solution. Missing features include (1) dynamic filters for nodes with certain Slurm features, that belong to specific Slurm partitions, or have a running job on them, (2) actions when clicking on a node that, without leaving the page, provide additional insights into running jobs or historical data, (3) additional components that the Slurm API enables, providing simple insight into historical jobs without something more

powerful like XDMoD [15]. A major lesson learned from this second-generation Plotly-powered node status page was how to make applications accessible to Open OnDemand users, which any new implementation must carry forward.

The code for this application is available in the supplement and is open source [1].

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I’d like to thank Lee Reynolds, for the initial design and implementation of the PHP concise status page that worked so well for so long. Thank you to Johnathan Lee for help with the Salt stack, providing meaningful feedback on the final look of the status page (like to include the queue statistics), and setting up the system status OOD app. Thank you to William Dizon for the discussions on how to improve the previous status page with features and backend efficiency. Thank you to Douglas Jennewein for allowing the status page into production and asking for a status page description legend. Thank you to Martin Cuma, Alan Chalker, and the community for the interest and suggestions for the status page.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jason Yalim. Sol status page, 2023. <https://github.com/jyalim/sol-status-page>.
- [2] Douglas M. Jennewein, Johnathan Lee, Chris Kurtz, Will Dizon, Ian Shaeffer, Alan Chapman, Alejandro Chiquete, Josh Burks, Amber Carlson, Natalie Mason, Arhat Kobwala, Thirugnanam Jagadeesan, Praful Barghav, Torey Battelle, Rebecca Belshe, Debra McCaffrey, Marisa Brazil, Chaitanya Inumella, Kirby Kuznia, Jade Buzinski, Sean Dudley, Dhruvil Shah, Gil Speyer, and Jason Yalim. The sol supercomputer at arizona state university. In *Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing*, PEARC ’23, New York, NY, USA, 2023. Association for Computing Machinery.
- [3] ASU. Sol, 2023. <https://github.com/ASU-KE/Sol>.
- [4] Plotly Technologies Inc. Collaborative data science, 2015.
- [5] Dave Hudak, Doug Johnson, Alan Chalker, and et al. Open ondemand: A web-based client portal for hpc centers. *J. of Open Source Software*, 3(25):622, 2018.
- [6] Prometheus. Prometheus, 2024. <https://github.com/prometheus/prometheus>.
- [7] Influxdata. Telegraf, 2024. <https://github.com/influxdata/telegraf>.
- [8] Influxdata. Influxdb, 2024. <https://github.com/influxdata/influxdb>.
- [9] Ganglia. Ganglia, 2024. <https://github.com/ganglia>.
- [10] Grafana. Grafana, 2024. <https://github.com/grafana/grafana>.
- [11] Nitin Sukhija and Elizabeth Bautista. Towards a framework for monitoring and analyzing high performance computing environments using kubernetes and prometheus. In *2019 IEEE SmartWorld, Ubiquitous Intelligence & Computing, Advanced & Trusted Computing, Scalable Computing & Communications, Cloud & Big Data Computing, Internet of People and Smart City Innovation (SmartWorld/SCAL-COM/UIC/ATC/CBDCom/IOP/SCI)*, pages 257–262, 2019.
- [12] Jie Li, Ghazanfar Ali, Ngan Nguyen, Jon Hass, Alan Sill, Tommy Dang, and Yong Chen. Monster: An out-of-the-box monitoring tool for high performance computing systems. In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Cluster Computing (CLUSTER)*, pages 119–129, 2020.
- [13] Andy B. Yoo, Morris A. Jette, and Mark Grondona. Slurm: Simple linux utility for resource management. In Dror Feitelson, Larry Rudolph, and Uwe Schwiegelshohn, editors, *Job Scheduling Strategies for Parallel Processing*, pages 44–60, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2003. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [14] Salt Stack. Salt, 2024. <https://github.com/saltstack/salt>.
- [15] Jeffrey T. Palmer, Steven M. Gallo, Thomas R. Furlani, and et al. Open xdmoc: A tool for the comprehensive management of high-performance computing resources. *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 17(4):52–62, 2015.